

Control Linked Tetradrachms in the Name of Andragoras and Sophytes: The Significance of a Previously Undocumented Tetradrachm Issue of Andragoras.

Parthia, Andragoras, c. 250-238 BC

AR Tetradrachm (17.04g, 25 mm, 6h)

struck c. 245-238 BC

OBV: Head of Tyche wearing mural crown, ΛP (largely off-flan) behind, all within a dotted border.

REV: $\text{AND}\Delta\text{P}\Lambda\text{G}\text{O}\text{P}\text{O}\text{Y}$ to r., Athena standing l. holding owl in r. hand, the other hand resting on a vertical shield decorated with a Medusa head, grounded spear, point downward crossing diagonally behind, *kerykeion* in l. field, all within a dotted border.

REF: Taylor, *Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 6 var. A previously unrecorded variety with the *Kerykeion* symbol mint control.

Roma Numismatics XIV (21 Sep. 2017), lot 327.

This coin bears the ΛP mint control behind the neck of Tyche on the obverse. The mint control, although struck largely off-flan, is known from an obverse die matched example of Taylor, *Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 6.3, which carries no reverse mint control.

The *Kerykeion* symbol mint control on the reverse of this coin is previously undocumented. Its presence on this coin serves to directly control link the Andragoras issues (Series 6) with the succeeding issues struck in the name of Sophytes; the Athena /Cockerel (Series 7) and the Helmeted Male Head/Cockerel (Series 8) issues, both of which bear an identical *Kerykeion* mint control in the left field of the reverse (Figure 1).

Furthermore, the *kerykeion* confirms the relative chronology of the Andragoras issue (Series 6) with the last of the Athena/Eagle (Series 3.6-3.7) emission, which bears the *Kerykeion* symbol accompanied by a vine branch. Previously attributed to Sophytes, Series 3 is more correctly attributed to Andragoras as proposed by Taylor (2019).

Recognition of this previously unknown variety of Series 6 completes the coherency of the control linked sequence of issues belonging to the period of Andragoras, the satrap of Parthia, who was briefly succeeded by Sophytes in the closing stage of the Parni conquest of Parthia led by Arsaces I.

Reference: Taylor, L. W. H. "Birds of a Feather, Brothers in Arms: The Coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes." *American Journal of Numismatics* 31 (2019): 21-79.

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Figure 1. *Kerykeion* control linked Andragoras and Sophytes Tetradrachms.

Andragoras (Taylor, *Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 6)

Sophytes (Taylor, *Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 7)

Sophytes (Taylor, *Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 8)

